

ON THE ANALYTICAL APPLICATIONS OF DUTOIT'S THERMO-VOLUMETRY: ESTIMATION OF AMINO-ACIDS

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The thermometric method has been employed in the estimation of some biologically important amino-acids, both individually and in mixtures, by titration with NaOH. The method is rapid and non-specific and the results obtained agree within 1% of the theoretical values.

The usefulness of thermometric titration in ascertaining the stages of ionisation of the polybasic acids was first shown by Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1922, 19, 324, 331), who titrated H_2SO_4 and H_3PO_4 with NaOH and obtained in the thermometric diagrams, inflexions indicating the stagewise replacement of H^+ by Na^+ . Later, Mondain-Monval and Paris (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1938, v, 5, 1641) titrated a number of other acids including H_3AsO_3 , H_3AsO_4 and H_3BO_3 with NaOH, obtaining definite evidence of the formations of NaH_2AsO_3 , NaH_2AsO_4 , Na_2HAsO_4 , Na_2AsO_4 and NaH_2BO_3 in solution. Recently Paris and Robert (*ibid.*, 1943, 10, 224) and Tardy and Paris (*ibid.*, 1945, 12, 16) have applied thermometric method in the estimation of mixtures of oxy-acids of phosphorus by a single titration with NaOH.

The determination of the basicity of a polybasic acid by the thermometric method is obviously due to the large differences in the heats of ionisation corresponding to the successive stages of the dissociation of the acid molecule. The same reason also accounts for the applicability of the method in the estimation of the acid mixtures. The above considerations have led the authors to test the applicability of thermometric titration in the estimation of some biologically important amino-acids, in view of the fact that except the formol titration method of Sørensen, other methods, which are based on changing the physical surroundings of the ampholytes, are of limited applicability, and hence, they are of little value from the analytical standpoint.

Attempt has been made to titrate both $-COOH$ and $-NH_2$ with NaOH and HCl respectively. Though considerable success has been attained in the estimation of the acid group, both for the individual acid as well as of their mixtures, the method failed in the titration of the basic part due to the smallness of the heat change.

EXPERIMENTAL

Stock solutions of glycine (0.23 N), alanine (0.1134 N), glutamic acid (0.08965 N) and aspartic acid (0.0725 N) were prepared by dissolving in distilled water accurately weighed samples of Merck's A.R. amino-acids, which were purified by recrystallising twice from distilled water and drying at 100° in the air-oven.

These solutions were employed for the titration of the individual amino-acid with a standard NaOH solution. Solutions of the amino-acids at different concentrations were prepared by the requisite dilution of the stock solutions with distilled water.

A second set of stock solutions of glycine (0.1002 N), alanine (0.0782 N), glutamic acid (0.0863 N) and aspartic acid (0.0644 N) were prepared by the same method as above.

These solutions were employed in the titrations of the mixtures of the amino-acids at different compositions.

A stock solution of 2*N*-NaOH in freshly distilled water was prepared by dissolving E. Merck's NaOH, and standardising against 0.098 *N*-H₂SO₄ using phenolphthalein indicator. The stock alkali solution was diluted to various strengths with distilled water, the solutions being immediately restandardised before employing them in the thermometric titration of the amino-acid.

The thermometric apparatus and the method of titration were the same as Dutoit's. The individual acids or their mixtures (50-100 c.c.) were employed for titration (*loc. cit.*).

In Tables I-III the results of the thermometric titrations of the amino-acids have been summarised. The titrations are very well reproducible, as has been shown by duplicate experiments.

The thermometric curves (Figs. 1-5) have been drawn by plotting the heat changes at constant volume ΔT_{cv} against the volume of the titre added. Here

$$\Delta T_{cv} = \frac{\Delta T (V + dv)}{V'}$$

where ΔT = observed change in temperature, V = the initial volume in c. c. of the solution in the Dewar and dv is the volume in c.c. of the titre added). This method of plotting is due to Chatterjee (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 366).

The compositions of the acid mixtures have been calculated in the following way :

Dibasic acid. Volume of the titre at first inflexion $\times$ strength of the base $\times$ M. W. of the dibasic acid = wt. in g. of the dibasic acid per litre.

Monobasic acid. (Volume of the titre at the second inflexion $- 2 \times$ volume of the titre at the first inflexion) $\times$ M.W. of the monobasic acid = wt. in g. of the monobasic acid per litre.

TABLE I
Thermometric titrations of amino-acids with NaOH.

End points.	Glycine (Fig. 1).		Alanine (Fig. 2).		Glutamic acid (Fig 3).		Aspartic acid (Fig.4)		
	Curve (a).	Curve (b).	Curve (a).	Curve (b).	Curve (a).	Curve (b).	Curve (a).	Curve (b).	
Thermometric (c.c.)	11.4	5.7	11.35	5	6.1	4.5	5.3	4.75	3.2
					9	8.9	10.6	9.55	6.4
Theoretical (c.c.)	11.42	5.74	11.42	5	6.07	4.45	5.41	4.80	3.125
						8.9	10.82	9.59	6.25
% Error in thermometry	+ 0.2	-0.75	- 0.64	Nil	+0.5	+1.12%	- 1.6%	-0.5	+2.7

TABLE II
Thermometric titration of mixtures of amino-acids with NaOH (Fig. 5)

End-points.	Curve (a).	Curve (b).	Curve (c).
Thermometric (c.c.)	4.5	3.65	3.4
	14.4	11.40	9.8
Theoretical (c.c.)	4.509	3.607	3.37
	14.25	11.40	10.00
% Error :			
First inflexion	-0.2 %	+1.3 %	1.2 %
Total	+1%	Nil	-2%

TABLE III

Composition of the mixtures of amino-acids from thermometric titration curves (Fig. 5).

	Glycine		Glutamic acid		Alanine.	Aspartic acid.
	Curve (a)	Curve (b).	Curve (a).	Curve (b).	Curve (c).	Curve (c).
Found (in g.)	0.1915	0.1504	0.3167	0.2569	0.1393	0.2166
Actually present (in g.)	0.1872	0.1498	0.3175	0.2540	0.1393	0.2145
% Error	+ 2.26	+0.4	-0.25	+1.14	+0.014	+0.93

DISCUSSION

It will be seen from the Figs. 1-5 and Tables I-III that the thermometric titration curves of the individual amino-acids as well as those of mixtures of these acids are all characterised by sharp end-points, which agree within 2% (usually less) of the theoretical

FIG 1

values. As a method of estimation of the potential acidity of these substances in aqueous medium within the range of concentration employed (0.2 N - 0.03 N acids), thermometric titration with NaOH therefore presents considerable promise. The basicity is clearly indicated by the number of inflexions arising in the thermometric diagrams. In the curves of the dicarboxylic acids, viz., glutamic and aspartic acids (Figs. 3 & 4), the difference in the extent of the ionisation of the two carboxyl groups is also reflected in the difference in the slopes of the intersecting straight lines. As expected, the first half of the curve is steeper than the other half, showing that the rate of heat change during the replacement of the first H^+ is greater than that of the second. In fact, the first acid dissociations of glutamic and aspartic acids ($pK_1 = 4.2$ and $pK_1 = 3.8$ respectively) are strong enough to be titrated directly by potentiometric method. In the same way, differences in the acid strengths of the mono- and the dicarboxylic acids are indicated in their thermometric titration curves.

FIG 2

In the case of the mixtures of a mono- and a dicarboxylic acid, the breaks in the thermometric diagrams are also in accord with the magnitudes of the dissociation constants of these acids. Since the second dissociation constants of glutamic and aspartic

FIG 3

acids ($pK_2 = 9.8$ and $pK_3 = 9.9$ respectively) are very nearly equal to those of glycine and alanine ($pK = 9.7$ in both cases), it follows that the acid salt of the dibasic acid and the monobasic acid should be simultaneously neutralised by NaOH and the end-point of the titration will be due to the total acids present in the system. The two breaks arising in

the thermometric titration curves of the mixtures (Fig. 5) occur in their expected positions, the first one indicating the formation of the acid salt of the dicarboxylic acid, the other one giving the total acid content of the mixtures.

FIG 4

The explanation of the failure of thermometric titration by HCl in the estimation of the amino group due to the smallness of the heat change, is also provided if we consider the values of the heats of formation of the Zwitterion acid ZH^+ and the Zwitterion base ZOH^- respectively. These values, which have been determined by Owen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 24) and Sturtevant (*ibid.*, 1941, 63, 88; 1942, 64, 762) from measurements of the temperature coefficients of the ionisation constants and the heats of reactions of glycine and *dl*-alanine with HCl and NaOH respectively, show that the heat of the formation of the Zwitterion base ZOH^- is considerably larger than the corresponding values for the formation of the Zwitterion acid ZH^+ .

FIG 5

The thermometric method of the estimation of the amino-acids so far developed is simple, quick, fairly accurate and non-specific. It thus combines all the features of a generalised method, its only limitation being that it cannot be carried out at very low concentrations due to the difficulty in the accurate determination of extremely small heat changes, with the present equipment.

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N.B. The results of the thermometric titrations of the amino-acids have expediently been interpreted from classical standpoint due to the inadequacy of the Zwitterion concept as applied to the dicarboxylic amino-acids in general.